

SHORT NOTES

Chromatographic Study of Anionic Complexes : Separation of Some Ions in the Presence of Oxalate Using Methanol as Solvent

Eric John Singh and Arun K. Dey

In previous communications (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1958, 159, 332; 1959, 165, 81, 179; *J. Chromatog.*, 1959, 2, 95; 1960, 3, 146; *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., India*, 1959, 28A, 43, 138; this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 235, 763; XVII Int. Cong. Pure and Appl. Chem., Munich, 1959, Abstract No. A 1077) the attempted separation of metal ions in presence of tartrate, citrate, and oxalate, using aqueous alcohols as solvent has been described. This paper records our observations on the chromatographic separation of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Fe(II), and Cd(II) in mixtures in presence of oxalate, using 50% aqueous methanol as solvent.

Procedure.—Solutions of metal salts and of potassium oxalate were prepared and standardised as described earlier. The results are summarised below. The conditions of experiments were identical to those described previously (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 763).

In the mixtures, shown in Tables I and II, a solution containing $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and H_2S was used for developing in all the cases except in mixtures containing nickel, where dimethylglyoxime was also used.

TABLE I

Separation of Cu(II) from Co(II), Cd(II), Ni(II) Fe(II), or, Fe(III).

	Effective separation with optimum conc. of oxalate added.	Observation.
Cu(II)—Co(II)	0.7 equiv.	No separation possible beyond opt. conc.
Cu(II)—Cd(II)	0.9	Do
Cu(II)—Ni(II)	0.4	Do
Cu(II)—Fe(II)	0.6	Do. A part of the metal precipitating.
Cu(II)—Fe(III)	0.5	Do. Most of Cu(II) is found at the initial point.

TABLE II

Separation of mixtures.

	Effective separation with optimum conc. of oxalate.	Observation.
Co(II)—Cd(II)	0.9 equiv.	With ratio 1:2.5 or above Cd^{2+} ions do not move at all.
Ni(II)—Fe(III)	1.3	No separation beyond opt. conc.
Co(II)—Fe(II)	1.3	Do
Fe(II)—Fe(III)	1.3	Do

Separation of Co(II), Cd(II), and Cu(II)

FIG. 1

A part of the metal precipitates in all the systems. Separation of the cations was observed up to 0.35 equivalents of oxalate added, beyond which no separation was effected. In case of copper (II), tailing occurred in the chromatograms as shown by the R_T values. The R_L values of the metal ions of Co(II), Cd(II), and Cu(II) behaved in a similar manner as recorded earlier (Fig. 1)

Separation of Co(II), Cu(II), and Fe(III)

FIG. 2

In the beginning no precipitation occurred in the systems, but when 0.313 or more equivalents of oxalate were added, a part of the metal was precipitated. The separation of all the three ions was possible up to the addition of 0.53 equivalents of oxalate, but with higher concentrations of the same, only the separation of Co(II) and Fe(III) was effected because Cu(II) was completely precipitated.

Separation of Co(II) and Fe(III) was possible up to one equivalent of the complexing agent added; but on increasing the concentration of the same, no separation was effected. The minimum R_L value of Cu(II) was obtained with the addition of 0.313 equivalents of oxalate. The R_L value of Co(II) becomes constant, when 0.47 equivalents of the complexing agent are added (Fig. 2).

Separation of Fe(II), Cu(II), and Fe(III)

Separation of the three metal ions was observed up to the addition of 0.70 equivalents of oxalate, but with ratios 1 : 0.76 to 1 : 1, separation occurred in a diffused state. With higher concentrations of oxalate no separation was possible. With the ratios 1 : 0 to 1 : 0.313 the sequence of separation is: Fe(II), Cu(II)-Fe(III), but with the ratios 1 : 0.39 to 1 : 0.76 the sequence of separation is Fe(II)-Fe(III)-Cu(II). With the ratios 1 : 0.53 to 1 : 0.76 copper (II) ions do not move at all, whereas other ions move upwards.